

Quantum Bound State and Time-Removed Impulse Picture

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 27, 2023

In (1), we argued that classically there are two pictures. The impulse picture $\Delta p = \int dt F$ does not distinguish between different velocities if p is the same. In other words, $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$ (so time is removed) and v_1 and v_2 create the same impulse (and quantum mechanically the same interference/diffraction pattern) even though v_1 and v_2 are physical and different.

The second classical picture is the kinetic energy-work one which depends explicitly on time i.e. $v dp = F dx$. The two pictures are consistent, but for the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem, a photon count and photon energy balance equation based on time are not independent. Thus one must go to the time-removed impulse picture in order to have two equations, based on the probability $\exp(ipx)$, in order to solve the problem.

We concluded in (1) that an impulse picture with time removed is necessary to describe interactions in a quantum system in a steady state scenario. Thus this picture should be applied to a bound state. A quantum bound state, however, makes use of a potential $V(x)$ which is associated classically with a kinetic energy at x . Kinetic energy depends on time so how is this described in the impulse picture? We argue that one creates an average of pp based on the impulse probability $\exp(ipx)$ $a(p)$ ($a(p)$ is a weight for p) which has time removed. It is the impulse probability $\exp(ipx)$ which allows for interference to occur. As a result, $\langle pp \rangle$ does not have time present and may include p and $-p$ values which classically would occur during different time intervals.

Once $\langle pp \rangle$ is computed in the time-removed picture, however, one divides by $1/2m$ (in the nonrelativistic case) to create kinetic energy. Thus $p_{rms}(x)$, a mathematical average, may be associated with the idea of motion in space and time. $p_{rms}(x)$, however, may not be considered physical as it is the impulses and $\exp(ipx)$ which are physical.

As argued in (1), however, classically the two pictures should be consistent. As a result, for high energy levels, the description of $\langle pp \rangle$ in terms of an impulse picture which does not include time, but then adds $1/2m$ at the end should be equivalent to a picture in which a particle moves either to the left or right. We suggest that at high energy levels, one may actually assign $p_{rms}(x)$ as a physical quantity within a tiny dx and follow the particle in time. Even in the time-removed impulse picture, there is velocity i.e. motion in time. It is just not used to calculate interaction averages in a steady state scenario.

We suggest that to move from the quantum picture to the classical, one switches formalisms i.e. drops the impulse- time removed picture and uses the time dependent motion in one direction. These two pictures are consistent at the classical level i.e. the classical time picture is a good approximation to the detailed impulse time removed picture which is now occurring in tiny dx regions.

The Question of Time in Quantum Free Particle Interactions

A quantum free particle has a velocity which may be measured. Thus the notion of motion in space and time exists. The issue seems to be that one may not need to track time when calculating certain interactions. For example, $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ both yield the same physical impulse classically and quantum mechanically and create the same diffraction/interference pattern quantum mechanically.

In quantum mechanics, however,, there could be physical interaction situations in which time is important. For example, two quantum particles with $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ may start at the same time and move towards a target. The faster particle may break through the target so that the slower one does not interact with the target which is no longer there. This is a time dependent problem in quantum mechanics.

Steady state problems, however, like one dimensional reflection/refraction are not time-dependent in this manner. They may be described by either a photon count balance which is not independent of an energy or pressure balance. Describing a steady state photon count balance by:

$$AA/c = BB/c + CC/ c_2 \text{ where } c_2=c/n_2 \text{ } n_2= \text{index of refraction and } n_1=1 \text{ ((1))}$$

does not allow one to solve for B,C in terms of A even though there is nothing wrong with ((1)). We argued in (1) that one needs to switch to an impulse picture which drops time (i.e. velocities) to solve this problem. Such an impulse picture uses $\exp(ipx)$ as its free particle impulse (time-removed) probability and leads to two independent equations:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \text{ ((2a)) and}$$

$$Ap \exp(ipx) - Bp \exp(-ipx) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \text{ ((2b))}$$

These two equations, however, combine to create ((1)) showing the consistency between the two approaches. Nevertheless, the impulse time-removed picture must be used to solve the steady stream one dimensional reflection/refraction problem.

A quantum bound state, we argue, is like a steady stream problem and so should also be solved using the time removed impulse probability $\exp(ipx)$. This, however, does not mean that time is really removed and that there are no velocities. It means that interactions may be described by removing time. This seems to imply that p and $-p$ may be combined when creating impulse time-removed averages even though classically a particle moves either to the right or left. This will become an issue when dealing with high energy levels.

Quantum Bound State

The quantum bound state seems to be somewhat unusual. A potential $V(x)$ from classical physics is of ten used which implies an average kinetic energy $KE(x)$ which adds to $V(x)$ to create a constant E (energy). This, however, implies a time based picture, but in the above section we suggested that one dimensional photon reflection/refraction is based on an impulse

time-removed picture. How can one have a time-removed impulse and a time based $KE(x)$ picture at the same time? This is possible if one uses the impulse time-removed picture to calculate $\langle pp \rangle$ i.e. this average is calculated based on the impulse probability $\exp(ipx)$. No time is present in such a picture and so p and $-p$ values are used together. After obtaining $\langle pp \rangle$, which is a mathematical average, one may divide by $2m$ (nonrelativistically) to obtain $KE(x)$ which is a mathematical average created from a time removed physical impulse picture. { Relativistically one has for the Klein-Gordon case: $E^2 = \langle pp \rangle + m^2 c^4$, so m_0 is again simply a parameter and one uses the impulse time-removed picture except for the fact that m_0 again effects the overall average $\langle pp \rangle$ which describes the physical impulses which occur in a time-removed manner i.e. include p , $-p$. }

Thus:

$$\left\{ \sum_{p} a(p) p \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum_{p} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} \frac{1}{2m} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((3))$$

Or $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W + V(x) = E_n$, where $W = \sum_{p} a(p) \exp(ipx)$ ((4))

One may think of the average $prms(x)$ as moving in space and time, but this bypasses the physical impulse picture of time removed and impulse hits occurring in x with a probability of $\exp(ipx)$.

The question becomes: What does one do in the high energy level limit?

High Energy Level Limit

Classically, $\Delta KE = \int F dx$ and $\Delta p = \int F dt$. The former uses motion in time, the latter is based on time-removed impulses. Both are consistent, however, We suggest that in the high energy level limit, the $\exp(ipx)$ picture (impulse time-removed picture) creates crests/troughs which are so narrow as to fit into a tiny dx i.e a region tiny with respect to the length between classical turning points. $prms(x)$, however, may have a wavelength \hbar/p which also fits within dx . Thus what was once a mathematical average linked with motion in time and space has physical meaning as motion in one direction and so is physically real.

The impulse time-removed picture was used in order to calculate properly interactions, but for high energy levels, one cannot argue that there is no time in the picture nor directional motion. Thus one may switch from the $\exp(ipx)$ impulse time-removed picture to the time dependent kinetic energy picture using $prms(x)$ as a good approximation. In other words, interactions with $V(x)$ in the impulse picture are occurring in a tiny dx region and so one may approximate and use Newton's picture.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that from (1), the one dimensional photon reflection-refraction problem shows that quantum free particle interactions occur in an impulse time-removed manner which is consistent with a work-energy picture. The reflection-refraction problem is a steady state problem and we argue that a quantum bound state is also steady state. Interactions in a bound

problem should occur using an impulse time-removed picture. The problem is that $V(x)$, a potential, often from classical physics, is used in a bound state problem. It is associated with an average kinetic energy $KE(x)$ which depends on time i.e. motion in space and time. Physical impulses, however, occur according to the probability $\exp(ipx)$ which has time removed and includes $p, -p$. One may calculate $\langle pp \rangle$ in the time-removed impulse picture, and finally divide by $1/2m$ nonrelativistically. This creates a $prms(x)$ which is a mathematical byproduct of the physical impulse picture. It is a mathematical byproduct as it does not show the physical impulse manner in which interactions occur.

As energy levels, however, become high, the wavelength of $prms(x)$, $\hbar/prms(x)$, fits within a tiny dx . In such a case, one does not need the details of the impulses $\exp(ipx)$ which also occur within dx and one may switch, we argue, from the time-removed impulse picture to a time present $prms(x)$ one where $prms(x)prms(x)/2m + V(x) = E$ shows motion in one direction at a given time.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Features from Time-Independence of Impulse Balance in the Photon Reflection/Refraction Problem Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2023)